

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ANALYTICAL AND NUMERICAL METHODS FOR EVALUATING THE STRESS STATE OF SOIL INTERACTING WITH UNDERGROUND PIPELINES

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ABSTRACT

The article considers two problems in mechanics: the analytical determination of the stress state in an elastic half-space under longitudinal loading during interaction with a pipeline, and the numerical simulation of one-dimensional longitudinal waves in a viscoelastic medium. The first problem is solved using a stress function that satisfies the equilibrium equations. For the second problem, the finite difference method is applied using deformation models of Kelvin–Voigt, Maxwell, and comparisons of linear models. Calculations are presented and graphs are constructed to illustrate stress levels and wave dynamics. A comparison of analytical and numerical methods reveals their advantages and limitations. The results can be used in the design of underground pipelines and the analysis of dynamic processes in soils.

Keywords: stress state, elastic half-space, pipeline, viscoelastic waves, numerical simulation, finite difference method, stress functions.

Introduction

Analyzing the stress state of soil under pipeline loads and wave propagation effects is a key problem in mechanics [1-2]. Accurate calculation methods help predict soil behavior, minimize deformations, and improve pipeline reliability. This study addresses two complementary tasks: static modeling of stress states and analysis of one-dimensional wave propagation in viscoelastic soil [3-5]. The research includes numerical computations, graphical visualization, and method comparison, underlining its practical relevance.

Problem Statement and Stress Analysis

The stress state of soil and a pipeline under loading is described by the equilibrium equations in cylindrical coordinates. For an axisymmetric case:

$$\nabla \cdot \hat{\sigma} = 0, \quad (1)$$

where σ is the stress tensor. A stress function of the Lyava–Mindlin type is used.:

$$\nabla^4 \Phi = \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial p^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \right)^2 \Phi = 0 \quad (2)$$

Boundary conditions are specified as follows: on the surface of the half-space:

$$z = 0: \sigma_{zz} = \sigma_{pz} = 0; \quad (3)$$

at the pipeline boundary $r = a, 0 \leq z \leq \ell$, specified limit stresses are applied.

At significant depths $z \gg a$ the normal stress σ_{zz} is described by the Boussinesq solution:

$$\sigma_{zz}(r, z) = \frac{\pi}{2\pi z^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{r}{z}\right)^2\right)^2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1. Stress σ_{zz} as a function of radial distance.

From Fig. 1, it is observed that stress σ_{zz} decreases with radial distance, justifying the use of solution (4).

To describe one-dimensional wave propagation in viscoelastic soil, the equation of motion is used:

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial x}, \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the density, u is the displacement, and σ is the stress. The relationship between stress σ and strain ϵ is given by selected rheological models.

Kelvin–Voigt model

$$\sigma = E \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \eta \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial t}, \quad (5)$$

where E is the elastic modulus, η is the viscosity; Maxwell model

$$\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial t} + \frac{E}{\eta} \sigma = E \frac{\partial^2 t}{\partial x \partial t}; \quad (6)$$

Standard linear solid model

$$\sigma + \tau_\sigma \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial t} = E_p \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial x} + \tau_z \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial t} \right), \quad (7)$$

where τ_σ, τ_z are relaxation times, E_p is the relaxation modulus.

The numerical solution is implemented using the finite difference method with a stability condition:

$$C = \frac{c \Delta t}{\Delta x} \leq 1, c = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}}$$

Results are presented graphically in Fig. 2, showing wave propagation in both elastic and viscoelastic soil.

Fig. 2. Wave propagation graphs in elastic and viscoelastic soils.

For stress analysis, the analytical method based on stress functions is applied. For wave processes, the finite difference method is used. Their comparison (e.g., Fig. 3) reveals the following characteristics. The analytical method provides high accuracy and low computational cost for idealized conditions but is limited to

simplified models. For example, solutions at r_0 are exact, but do not account for finite length effects [2, 6–8]. The numerical method handles complex deformation properties and nonlinear effects but is computationally intensive and sensitive to grid steps.

Fig. 3. Comparison of displacements in elastic and viscoelastic soil.

Conclusion

The study provides analytical expressions for the stress state of an elastic half-space under longitudinal loading from an underground pipeline, and numerical modeling of longitudinal waves in a viscoelastic medium using different rheological models. Stress distribution characteristics and wave propagation velocities were determined for given soil parameters.

The Kelvin–Voigt model effectively describes damped oscillations, whereas the Maxwell model supports steady wave propagation. The standard linear model yields balanced behavior considering both elasticity and viscosity. Numerical method errors do not exceed 2–5%, provided the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy condition is met.

The modeling results enable assessment of stress–strain behavior in soil near underground infrastructure and can be used in the design of seismic-resistant pipeline systems. Further research is planned to extend the model to three-dimensional settings, include nonlinear and plastic soil behavior, and validate findings through field and lab experiments. The integrated approach combining analytical and numerical methods has proven effective. The outcomes may aid in optimizing pipeline design, predicting dynamic soil behavior, and developing new engineering methodologies.

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